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Consumer Preferences for Mangoes with Geographical Indication Labels in Brazil

1 Introduction

Historically, fruit purchase and consumption was linked to cultural and regional habits. Individual preferences were driven by experience and were constrained to the few options available. Research, however, suggests that preferences, the factor which defines choice, may change rapidly (Lusk e Briggeman 2009). Recently, the increase in information available and the high number of affluent consumers have lead to a higher demand for quality at the moment of purchasing fruit. The factors responsible for the increase in the market importance of fruits in general can be mostly explained by the search by consumers for healthier and sustainable food, as well by the increase in the household income in several developing countries, opening new markets worldwide.

Although fruit is generally perceived as a healthy food, concern about the indiscriminate use of agrochemicals and the risk of presence of residuals have driven the need for increased controls and better quality assurance schemes in the supply chain, increasing the demand for traceable products and reliable suppliers. The need for food safety and product quality is widely acknowledged by the major players of the fruit chain, from producers to final consumers. Society in general is increasingly looking for more sustainable products, giving extra value for goods and companies that are concerned about the environment they act upon. Thus, the capacity of the food industry to translate these needs into practical and controllable measures is a critical factor in achieving success in a competitive agricultural sector. Finally, consumers, with their preferences for quality attributes and sustainable food products, have become key players (Dimech, Caputo and Canavari, 2011).

Several studies have investigated how consumers' willingness to purchase and to pay for fruits and vegetables is influenced by diverse attributes. As listed by Dimech, Caputo, and Canavari (2011), they were: (a) visual, smell and taste qualities (Ernst et al. 2006); health related components (Onozaka, Bunch, and Larson 2006); (Stefano Boccaletti and Nardella 2000); (c) environmental

attributes (Haghiri, Hobbs, and McNamara 2009); origin, local and farmers' support (Darby et al. 2007; Thilmany, Bond, and Bond 2008); Rodríguez-Ibeas 2007);

(d) labels and certification (Van Loo et al. 2011). In order to cope with the changes in the market, the fruit sector is looking into new ways for differentiating the products, and it has been commonly observed that there has been an increase of labels added to fruit. The provision of more information to the consumers, through certification or origin labels, as well as the information on quality aspects as varieties and nutritional value can be used as marketing tools; helping in product differentiation and positioning.

Geographical indication (GI) labels can be seen also as a tool to increase the sustainability of a production site, protecting biological resources and indigenous knowledge, helping the development of rural communities and adding better agricultural practices into the system in question (Rangnekar, 2004). GIs imply the belief that at least on a certain extent quality and value of a product is intimately linked with a place where it is grown/produced/processed; in fact, Article 22.1 of the TRIPS Agreement (http://www.wipo.int/edocs/mdocs/sct/en/sct_9/sct_9_4.pdf) defines “geographical indications” as: “indications which identify a good as originating in the territory of a [WTO] Member, or a region or locality in that territory, where a given quality, reputation or other characteristic of the good is essentially attributable to its geographical origin.” This is a well-known signal of quality for many consumers and its use is heavily regulated in the European Union and in other countries (Giovannucci, Barham, and Pirog 2010).

However, only recently, developing countries are adopting legislations and actions regarding geographical indication labels (Guerra, 2010), and for the case of Brazil it has only been in place since the last decade. Also, fruit production is an important part of the prominent Brazilian agricultural sector and it has been growing at regular rates in the last years. In particular, fruits that were part of the export line had developed an intensive production system, resulting in a modern supply chain structure and better quality performance in terms of standardization and compliance

with market requirements. Mangoes are the best example of this development in Brazil. However, since in international markets the focus is mainly on standardized quality according to global standards, there is a concrete risk of losing important assets related to food diversity, specificity, cultural identity and tradition. In the last decade, the mango market in Brazil has grown more than 120%, achieving a total production of 1.272.184 tons of mangoes in an area around 80.000 ha. Apart from being an important fruit to the external market, the high national production contributes to the fact that a high share of the total amount produced is consumed in the domestic market. Taking into account the development of Brazil in the last few years and the country's tradition in agricultural production, this study is aimed at achieving a better knowledge of the preferences and willingness to pay for mango of Brazilian consumers; taking into consideration different fruit attributes as origin, varieties and packaging. We aim at evaluating the importance and value attributed to origin by Brazilian consumers, in order to evaluate whether they recognize this attribute as a relevant component of product's quality. This may be useful on two respects: for the policy decision makers, to know whether regulating the origin labeling may increase the welfare of consumers; and for the business decision makers, to know whether it is worth thinking to apply a legal protection to mango origin.

Research has been trying to assess how the consumers are valuing sustainable products and how the consumers themselves act and think regarding the theme. However, very few studies have been carried out on developing countries taking into consideration fresh fruit as a primary agricultural good, and consumer preferences for GI labels. In order to deal with this lack of information we carried out a choice experiment study in southeast Brazil among urban mango consumers. We analyzed the data using a random parameter logit model (RPL). Finally, using the results of the RPL model marginal willingness to pay (WTP) measures were calculated for different mango attributes such as variety, origin label and packaging.

2 Methodology: choice experiment approach

2.1 Experimental design

The construction of the experimental design starts with the selection of the product, definition of the attribute levels, and the identification of relevant alternatives that can accurately reproduce the real choice conditions in the market (Louviere, 2000). Mangoes have been selected as the product of interest for this CE study. The choice of mangoes as the main fruit for this study basically was mainly due to its importance in Brazilian export of fresh fruit, which means that the fruit production chain is well established and provides high quality product for both external and domestic market, for which consumers appear to be satisfied. The product was described by a series of attributes chosen according to the product characteristics generally used in product differentiation. According to Rombaldi et al. (2007), in south Brazil, the most relevant attributes among all fruits were price, appearance, origin and safety. Lusk and Briggeman 2009, provided a list of food value descriptions and the importance for consumers in the USA, relating safety, nutrition, taste and price as the most relevant, whilst origin was considered the least important attribute. However, for both researches the possibility to simply use the attributes identified is limited, since they were developed in a broad context and were not specific for the kind of fruit at hand.

In order to narrow the relevant attributes list, a focus group was conducted among Brazilian fruit consumers. The focus group is a method used to assess the opinion of a group of people regarding a subject, and its main advantage over questionnaires or interviews is the possibility of the discussion among the participants (Kitzinger 1994). At this step, 22 fruit consumers were introduced to the research topic and could contribute to the design of the survey. First, they were asked to indicate which fruit attributes they consider more important at the time of fruit purchasing, followed by a question regarding the awareness of fruit origin. At the end, they were presented to a preliminary version of the questionnaire, to test the comprehension of each question.

According to the main results obtained from the focus group, the final set of attributes chosen to be part of the Choice Experiment were: Price, Variety, Packaging and Origin. The levels of each attribute were then designed based on literature and feedback from the focus group. For the price attribute, the baseline price of R\$ 2,00 was set based on the price of mangoes in several shops of the region during the time of the survey, with premium prices of 10 and 20% (R\$ 2,20 and R\$ 2,40). At the focus groups it was observed that a higher price difference would be too high for the attributes chosen. Varieties were chosen based on the volume commercialized in distribution centres of Brazil, being Tommy Atkins, Palmer and Haden the most important ones (de Almeida, 2009). The alternative of not knowing the variety was also included. The attribute package was simply considered as presented in individual packaging or as exposed in bulk shelves. For the specific attribute of origin, considering that there is only one region with a registered GI, virtual labels of *Indicação de Procedência* (similar to PGI in the European Union) were created, indicating each one of the four main producing regions according to CEPEA (2010): Juazeiro/BA e Petrolina/PE, north of Minas Gerais, mid-west of Sao Paulo and southeast of Bahia. Finally, it was included one non-labelled option, indicating a situation where there was no information about the origin provided to the consumer. (see table 1 for more details).

The choice set design follows Street and Burgess (2007). First, using SPSS software a fractional factorial orthogonal design was selected to reduce the 120 original possible combinations of attributes and levels ($5 \times 3 \times 4 \times 2$) to 25 ‘treatments’. After this step, the number of choice sets has been determined and the first alternatives of these sets are given. Then, starting from this fractional factorial design, the generators for four attributes with 5, 4, 3 and 2 levels and two alternatives suggested by Street and Burgess (2007) resulted in twenty five pairs (choice sets), after discarding duplicates. The design is efficient and D-optimal, leading to a 92.5% efficient design according to D-efficiency.

Table 1 – Attributes and attribute levels s used on the choice experiment design.

Attributes	Levels considered			
PACKAGING	No packaging	exposed in Bulk shelves		
VARIETIES	<p>Manga Variedade Little esmeralda</p>			
GI LABELS				
PRICE	R\$ 1,40	R\$ 2,60	R\$ 3,80	

To avoid fatigue effects associated with multiple scenario valuation tasks, the 25 choice sets were randomly split into 5 blocks of 5 choice sets, and each block will be submitted to a different respondent. Once this step was complete, the design of the cards to be presented to the respondents was carried out. Together with the two possible buying options, it was included an opt-out (non-buying) alternative to help mitigate the effect of hypothetical bias, making the situation more similar to a real purchase scenario (Lusk and Schroeder 2004).

2.2 Theoretical models

Consumers' valuation of GI labels is analyzed within the choice modelling framework. Following this framework, consumers make a choice from a set of presented alternatives, which contain a number of attributes with different levels, combined within choice sets. According to random utility theory the n th consumer's utility of choosing option j in choice situation t can be represented as:

$$(1) U_{njt} = \beta_n' x_{njt} + \varepsilon_{njt}$$

Where x_{njt} is a vector of observed variables relating to alternative j and individual n in the specific choice task t ; β_n is a vector of structural parameters which characterizes choices by overall situation; ε_{njt} is the error term, which is assumed to be independent of β and x and unobserved by researchers. Depending on the different specifications of the density of unobserved factors $f(\varepsilon_{ijt})$ as well as the functional form of the representative utility, different choice models can be derived. The selection of this function will depend on the assumptions underlying consumer's preferences. If we assume homogeneity in terms of taste within the population, a multinomial logit model may be specified. However, if heterogeneity across consumers is expected, then MNL results are biased and hence models that can accommodate for heterogeneity in parameters should be specified. Since several consumer studies have pointed out that heterogeneity is an important issue in evaluating consumer preferences for credence attributes, a random parameter logit (RPL) was specified. According to Train (2003), if we consider a sequence of alternatives, one for each time period, $\mathbf{i} = (i_1, \dots, i_T)$, conditional on β the probability L_{ni} that individual n makes this sequence of choices is represented as:

$$(2) L_{ni}(\beta) = \prod_{t=1}^T \left[\frac{e^{\beta_n' x_{ni,t}}}{\sum_j e^{\beta_n' x_{nj,t}}} \right]$$

Since the error terms ε_{njt} 's are independent over time. Consequently, the unconditional probability is the integral of this product over all values of β :

$$(3) \mathbf{P}_{ni} = \int L_{ni}(\beta) f(\beta) d\beta$$

Because equation (3) lacks a closed form solution, following Train (2003) the parameters of the model are estimated by simulated maximum likelihood estimation techniques. Halton draws are

used in simulation because they have been shown to provide more efficient distribution of draws for numerical integration compared to random draws (Bhat, 2003).

Finally, the fact that Lancaster's utility theory is based on the assumption that consumers derive utility from consumption of the attributes permits a theoretically sound transformation of parameter estimates of each attribute into WTP measures. The WTP for attributes is the price change associated with a unit increase in a given attribute (Van Loo et al., 2011). In this application the estimates WTP is calculated as the ratio of the partial derivative of the utility function with respect to the attribute of interest (holding the other attributes fixed), divided by the derivative of the utility function with respect to the variable price.

3 Results

3.1 Data Collection

The survey was administered to Brazilian consumers in the city of Uberlandia (Brazil). Uberlandia is the second biggest city of the State of Minas Gerais, on southeast region, only after the State's capital. It is also the 30th biggest city in Brazil with more than 600.000 inhabitants (IBGE, 2010). The choice of Southeast region is related with its economic importance in the context of the country, as the region where most of consumers are concentrated, and the choice of Uberlandia relies on the facts that the city is one of the most important centres of logistics in the country and that its fruit distribution centre was the second in volume commercialized in Brazil.

A store intercept convenience sample (Malhotra, 1996) of about 215 adult food shoppers was randomly selected in four different grocery stores located in that city through face to face interviews. Specifically, in order to obtain a representative sample of consumers, the interviews were conducted in April 2011 during a period of two weeks, at different shopping hours and at four different fruit retail stores: a supermarket, a convenience market, a fruit and vegetable shop and at a farmers market, in order to capture different consumers segments. This spatial distribution is in line with the studies of Grebitus et. al. (2010) and (Menapace et al. 2011).

The socio-demographics characteristics of the respondents are shown in Table .

Table 2 - Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

<u>Gender</u>	Sample	BRAZIL	<u>Education (highest level achieved)</u>	Sample	BRAZIL
Male	21.9%	48.9%	Basic (primary school)	16.3%	49.7%
Female	78.1%	51.1%	Medium (secondary school)	33.0%	26.5%
			Higher (graduated from University)	50.7%	10.6%
<u>Age Group</u>			<u>State of birth</u>		
	0.9%		Minas Gerais	76.7%	10.3%
20 – 30	12.6%	26.6%*	Sao Paulo	7.4%	21.6%
30 – 50	46.5%	42.2%	Bahia	0.5%	7.3%
50 – 65	29.3%	19.3%	Pernambuco	0.5%	4.6%
Over 65	10.7%	10.9%	Others	14.9%	56.1%
<u>Household size (persons/household)</u>			<u>Household Monthly Income</u>		
Mean	3.13	3.3	R\$ 1000,00 or less	7.9%	21.6%
			R\$ 1.000,00 – R\$3.000,00	41.9%	46.8%
			R\$ 3.000,00 – R\$ 5.000,00	21.4%	15.4%
<u>Children at home</u>			R\$ 5.000,00 – R\$ 8.000,00	17.2%	7.2%
No children	61.4%	-	R\$ 8.000,00 – R\$ 12.000,00	7.9%	5.2%
One or more children	38.6%	-	More than R\$ 12.000,00	3.7%	3.8%

Source: IBGE (2010), IBGE (2009), IBGE (2009) and survey data.

* The percentages of the age groups of Brazilian population refer to people older than 20 years old.

As presented in the table, in comparison to Brazilian population females are overrepresented in the sample (78.1%). The high share of female respondents is explained by the fact that women are usually responsible for groceries and food shopping in Brazilian households, and since this survey was aimed to interview only actual fruit purchasers this characteristics of the sample is expected and positive. The age distribution shows that young people are under-represented whilst people between 50 – 65 years old are over-represented. The data above can also be correlated to the number of households with children. The household mean size (3.13) is very close to the value of the country (3.3), making a good comparison to the typical Brazilian family. The huge discrepancy among the education data, where the people with superior education achieved more than 50%, may be understood once Uberlandia is a university educational pole, with a federal university and several private institutions for higher education. The data for the household income compares well

to the Brazilian population distribution, with a slight tendency toward a higher income in the sample. This small difference must be due to the realization of the survey at the convenience market and at the supermarket located at a high class neighbourhood.

3.2 Consumer preferences and WTP for geographical indications labels

In the RPL model specified the utility that individual I obtains from alternative j is:

$$U_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 price_{ijt} + \beta_2 TommyAtkin_{ijt} + \beta_3 Palmer_{ijt} + \beta_4 Haden_{ijt} + \beta_5 Bulk_{ijt} + \beta_6 BA / PE_{ijt} + \beta_7 MG_{ijt} + \beta_8 SP_{ijt} + \beta_9 seBA_{ijt} + \varepsilon_{ijt}$$

Where j represents choice options A, B and C; β_0 is the constant for the non – buying option alternative, which equals 1 if respondent chooses not to buy any of the presented combination of Mango, and zero otherwise; . Price $_j$ is considered as a variable with an effect linear in the parameter and it refers to the purchase of 1 kg of fresh mangoes. All the other attributes entered the model as dummy variables that take the value 1 if they are present in option j and the value 0 otherwise. The baseline options that did not entered the model, for each attribute were: “no information on variety”, “packed fruit” and “no GI label”. Each model is estimated on a data set containing 1075 observations, relative to 215 respondents who were required to choose one option in every 5 different choice tasks. Table 3 shows the results from the estimations of the RPL model.

From the results of the econometric analysis it can be observed that the specific constant for the alternative C (non-buying option), is negative and statistically significant, suggesting that regarding the selected attributes the consumers prefer to buy the product instead of not buying any of the two alternative mangoes. The price coefficient is also negative and significant, implicating the consistency of the model with the theory of consumer demand, according to which the increase in price reduces the demand for a certain product. The coefficients for all the other attributes included in the experiment have significant and positive value, which indicates the utility of the product increase at the presence of every attribute considered, when compared to the baseline option.

Table 3 - RPL estimates

ESTIMATES		Coefficients	Std.Error	Wald - Values	p-Values
No_buy		-11.32***	1.59	-7.13	0.000
Price		4.42***	0.72	-6.16	0.000
Variety Tommy Atkins	Mean	1.29***	0.28	4.60	0.000
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>0.38</i>	<i>0.34</i>	<i>1.11</i>	<i>0.2656</i>
Variety Palmer	Mean	1.56***	0.38	4.60	0.000
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>1.94***</i>	<i>0.43</i>	<i>4.55</i>	<i>0.000</i>
Variety Haden	Mean	1.17***	0.32	3.45	0.002
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>0.80*</i>	<i>0.43</i>	<i>1.88</i>	<i>0.0607</i>
Bulk/Unpacked	Mean	0.36**	0.17	2.081	0.0374
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>1.41***</i>	<i>0.30</i>	<i>4.75</i>	<i>0.000</i>
GI Bahia/Pernambuco	Mean	0.62**	0.26	2.31	0.0208
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>1.58**</i>	<i>0.51</i>	<i>3.10</i>	<i>0.020</i>
GI Minas Gerais	Mean	0.67*	0.36	1.83	0.0669
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>3.02***</i>	<i>0.72</i>	<i>4.21</i>	<i>0.0000</i>
GI Sao Paulo	Mean	0.83**	0.33	2.52	0.0117
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>1.78***</i>	<i>0.42</i>	<i>4.27</i>	<i>0.000</i>
GI Sudeste Bahia	Mean	0.91***	0.31	2.99	0.0028
	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>1.79***</i>	<i>0.37</i>	<i>4.85</i>	<i>0.000</i>
N			1075		
LL			-752.3022		
McFadden Pseudo-R²			0.36		

Note: ***, **, * = Significance at 1%, 5%, 10% level, respectively.

Source: survey data.

However, some differences were found regarding the significance level and utility values amongst the attributes. Specifically, the different levels used to describe the variety attribute such as: Tommy Atkins, Palmer and Haden, show positive and statistically significant values, indicating that the utility associated to the purchasing of mangoes increases when information on the variety are available to consumers. These values are also higher than other parameters, such as packaging and GI label, indicating that among all attributes chosen in this study, the variety influences more the consumer at the act of purchasing mangoes. Amongst the varieties the highest utility was found for the Palmer, followed by Tommy Atkins and Haden. This preference was explained by de Almeida (2009) as the perception of consumers toward a high level of soluble solids and less fibres at the Palmer variety. The author also showed a trend on the increase of commercialization of the variety in Brazil.

As for the packaging attribute, the unpacked variable had a positive and significant value, suggesting preferences of Brazilian consumers for unpacked mangoes presented at bulk shelves. This finding is consistent with previous studies published in this area (FRUTIFATOS, 2003; Groot

and Albisu, 2010) and confirms the results obtained from the earlier discussed descriptive analysis according to which the packaging is found to be the least important attribute of fruit.

Regarding the indication of origin attribute, all the virtual labels created for this study presented a positive value, with variation on the level of importance. According to these results, it can be stated that consumers perceive an increase in utility for mangoes when they are labeled with a geographical indication revealing a specific Brazilian origin of the fruit chosen.

This result is consistent with the findings presented by Groot and Albisu (2010), for the Spanish peach market and by Menapace et al. 2011, for Canadian olive oil market, where they found an increase in utility for food products with a PGI label. Among the selected sample the preferred region was the southeast of Bahia, followed by Sao Paulo, Minas Gerais e BA/PE. It means that all virtual labels, referred to the production sites had a higher utility than the option with no GI label. However, during the pre test and focus group realized it was observed that the consumers are unaware of the production sites, which could indicate that the utility for the GI label is rather for the presence of the information of origin than for the specific preference for one region in particular.

The RPL estimates were then used to calculate the marginal WTP measures for each attribute.

Table 4 presents the marginal WTP and standard deviation for each of them.

It can be observed from the values, that the values are different from 0 at the significance level of 1% for the majority of attributes. The result suggests that Brazilian consumers are willing to pay a premium price for fresh mangoes with the information on variety (against no information), for unpacked fruits (against packed) as well for fruits with a geographical indication label (against no GI label) on it. The WTP is higher for the varieties, being the variety Palmer the one with the higher WTP an extra price for it. It may be associated with the quality perception for this variety specifically. A previous work by Combris et al. 2009 in Portugal stated that consumers of pears are more inclined to pay an extra price, varying from 0.11€ to 0.17€, for better taste and quality than for origin or certification information.

Table 4- Willingness to pay for fruit attributes among Brazilian consumers, based on the RPL model.

	<i>WTP</i>	
	<i>R\$ (BRL) for 1kg of fresh mangoes</i>	
<i>Variety Tommy Atkins</i>	0.29	***
<i>Variety Palmer</i>	0.35	***
<i>Variety Haden</i>	0.27	***
<i>Bulk/Unpacked</i>	0.08	**
<i>GI Bahia/Pernambuco</i>	0.14	**
<i>GI Minas Gerais</i>	0.15	*
<i>GI Sao Paulo</i>	0.19	**
<i>GI Sudeste Bahia</i>	0.21	***

^a WTP is derived from the model. WTP values are in R\$ (BRL) for 1kg of fresh mangoes.[†]

Note: ***, **, * = Significance at 1%, 5%, 10% level.

Source: survey data.

The GI labels also presented a significant WTP, indicating the preference of the consumers for fruits with certified origin in respect to the absence of information regarding the origin. This result is consistent with several studies that indicate the WTP a premium for food products with GI labels (Tsakiridou et al. 2011; Menapace et al. 2011).

Finally, the WTP for fruits presented at bulk shelves was positive, but with a lower value in comparison to the other variables.

4 Conclusion

In recent years, a growing interest from the consumer regarding the search for quality, safety and sustainability in food products has been registered and has led to several studies about the theme. Moreover, the social evolution of Brazil and its major position in the global market for agricultural goods corroborates for the need of such studies in the country. The main goal of this study was to identify the valuation given by Brazilian consumers to origin labels and other fruit attributes. At the best of our knowledge, no previous study has examined consumers' valuation for attributes as origin and varieties for mango fruits.

[†] Exchange rate of BRL in April 15th, 2011: 1 BRL = 0.6337 USD = 0.4395 EUR. Source: Thomson Reuters via UOL economia (available at: <http://economia.uol.com.br/cotacoes/cambio/>).

Results of the survey suggested that consumer choice can be influenced by the presence of GI origin labels as well as the information on the variety of the fruit. The utilities found for the attributes and the low value attributed to the choice of not buying any option available, confirms the validity of the attributes chosen. Specifically, the selected sample showed a high preference for the variety information, what can be seen as an indicator of quality. The reasons for such preference may include the fact that consumers prefer to purchase a known variety from which they perceive the quality it may offer than to purchase an unknown variety at all.

All the GI labels showed a positive utility, indicating that the presence of an origin label can be one extrinsic factor that collaborates to the product choice. This indicates an important tendency for the future, where the fruit labeling or branding can be an alternative way to create differentiation in the market.

The study of the WTP for mango attributes revealed that Brazilian consumers are willing to pay an extra price for more information, probably since more information may help the consumer to diminish the risk to purchasing something not complying with the expected quality.

Further studies using a consumer segmentation approach may reveal stronger preferences for some attributes during fruit purchasing, implying the use of new marketing policies for companies or producing regions. Hence, a better knowledge of preferences of each group may drive actions toward consumers' preferences; for example, classifying varieties according to specific target groups, and promoting marketing actions to increase the consumption within the group.

With regard to GI labels, the results of this study can raise some interest also among policy makers. The registration of the labels and the consequent marketing actions can be used to promote the development of rural areas, exploiting the uniqueness and protecting the genuineness of local products. On the other hand, it may also increase consumers' access to information regarding sustainability and could increase food safety by means of traceability practices included in the

production rules and compulsory when a GI is established. For local producers, the results obtained using the virtual GI labels may be worthy if they are planning whether registering a geographical indication or not.

In order to continue the discussion about the value given by consumers to labels regarding quality or sustainability more studies are required to assess the awareness of the society at large about the theme and how much consumers in general trust GI labels and are willing to pay for such attributes. Nevertheless, the Brazilian society continues to develop rapidly and in the current market situation this opportunity for introducing innovation in the fruit sector appears to be promising.

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